

Maxwell's Laws from Special Relativity, Lorentz Gauge and Spherical Symmetry in Rest Frame?

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In (1), we tried to derive Maxwell's laws from Gauss' law, the Lorentz gauge and special relativity. Here, we try to argue that one does not need Gauss' law, but only spherical symmetry of the charge distribution in the rest frame, the Lorentz gauge and special relativity. We argue that the Lorentz gauge is really a continuity equation for energy and momentum, using ϕ as energy and A as momentum. We try to present what we think are more general arguments for Gauss' law than what is given in (2).

Spherical Charge Distribution in a Rest Frame

Experimentally it is known that like charges repel and that this force is linked to the separation distance, if the source and test charge are at rest. For a spherical source charge distribution, one expects $F = q E(r)$ and for a conservative force, $E = -\text{grad } \phi$, from Newtonian mechanics. Here:

$$r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad ((1)) \quad \text{Here " " denotes the rest frame.}$$

From Newtonian mechanics, potential energy for a test charge q at rest is: $q \phi$ ((2))

((2)) is equivalent to rest mass and so should transform according to a Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{aligned} |g \quad v g| & \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } g = 1/\sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \\ |v g \quad g| & \end{aligned}$$

Thus: $(0, \phi) \rightarrow (A, \phi)$ where $\phi = g \phi(x, y, z)$ and $A = g v \phi(1, 0, 0)$ ((4))

In addition: $x = g(x - vt)$ and $t = g(-vx + t)$ ((5))

$E = -\text{grad } \phi - dA/dt$ partial and Spatial Isotropy

qE is force and is a measurable. If one were to use: $E = -\text{grad } \phi$ in the moving frame, then:

$$-\text{grad } \phi = \text{grad } g \text{ grad } \phi(r) = g e_i d\phi/dr \quad g g(x-vt)^2 + g e_j d\phi/dr^2 y + g e_k d\phi/dr^2 z \quad ((6))$$

Here e_i, e_j, e_k are unit vectors in the x, y, z directions.

There is a problem with ((6)) in that it does not represent isotropy in space because the e_i component is weighted by g , while the e_j and e_k are not. Put another way, it is not the vector that one would measure in the moving frame, but qE is a physical measurable, it is part of the

overall force $F = qE + qv \times B$ and the only force if a test charge is not moving or moving parallel to B .

To remedy this problem, one may use A ((4)) and:

$$E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial} \quad ((7))$$

This eliminates the g coefficient of $(x-vt)$ in the e_i portion.

Given that $q \phi$ is like rest mass, $q \phi$ should be moving mass and A momentum. If this is the case, one may propose a continuity equation ($c=1$):

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} \text{ partial} + \text{grad dot } A = 0 \quad ((8))$$

((8)) is called the Lorentz gauge.

One may define an object: $\text{grad } \times A = B$. At first, there may be no reason to do this, but we argue that A is a vector and $\frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial}$ measures time changes and returns a vector, so one should have a similar vector expression which measures gradient changes and returns a vector, i.e.

$$\text{Grad } \times A \quad ((9))$$

In previous notes, we have linked ((9)) to a force $qv \times B$. If A is momentum then $d \text{ momentum} / dt$ is force. $d/dt \rightarrow d/dt \text{ partial} + v \text{ dot grad}$. Here v is usually the velocity of the moving object, but A is a force field in space, even if it is created by a moving source charge and so one might qualitatively argue that one requires a second moving object (test charge) to bring in a velocity. An alternative approach is to note from ((4)) that $A = e_i g v \phi$ and $\text{grad } g \phi$ is a force, so A linked with grad must also be linked to a force. One still has to introduce the velocity v of a test charge in this approach.

Given ((9)), it immediately follows that: $\text{grad dot } B = 0$ ((10)).

$$\text{Given } E = -\text{grad } \phi - \frac{dA}{dt} \text{ partial and ((9)): } \text{grad } \times E = \frac{dB}{dt} \quad ((11))$$

What about $\text{grad dot } E$? It is known experimentally that E is proportional to the charge and that this does not depend on the size of a spherical distribution. In other words, a tiny point spherical charge q should create the same E field as a tiny point spherical charge half the size because there is no macroscopic way to measure either of the tiny sizes. In other words, both would be called a point charge and there would be one E formula for a point charge in a rest frame, corresponding to a ϕ . If one cannot distinguish tiny sizes of spherical charge distribution, we suggest that the same conclusion should hold for larger spherical charge distributions.

This would then lead to one value for E in the moving frame.

It is known that $\int dv \text{grad} \cdot E = \int \text{surface area} \cdot E$. One may postulate that this depends only on the charge inside, so $Q = \int dv \text{charge density}$, at least in the rest frame. This holds because one may choose any size volume, e.g. one sphere versus another. If the integral depended on a function of the radius of the sphere, it would not equal a constant Q.

Then: $\text{grad} \cdot E = \text{charge density constant}$ ((12)) for the rest frame

In order to determine the result for the moving frame without considering delta functions, one may note that:

$\text{Grad} \cdot E = -\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi - d/dt \text{partial} \text{grad} \cdot A = -\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} \phi + d/dt d/dt \text{partial} \phi$ ((12b)) using the Lorentz gauge

The integral of $\text{grad} \cdot E dv$ is an invariant in the rest frame, namely source charge. The D'Alembertian is an invariant and ϕ transforms as the fourth component of 4 vector from the rest frame, i.e. $\phi = \phi'' g$. Given that $x'' = g(x-vt)$, $dx = 1/g dx''$, so in the moving frame, the integral $dv \text{grad} \cdot E$ is also total charge suggesting that ((12)) holds in both the moving and rest frames.

This argument is similar to that given in (2), but (2) focuses more on the nature of the delta function. The above argument, we believe, is more general.

To obtain the last Maxwell equation: $E = -\text{grad} \phi - dA/dt \text{partial}$ and the Lorentz gauge i.e.

$dE/dt \text{partial} = -\text{grad} d\phi/dt \text{partial} - d/dt d/dt \text{partial} A = \text{grad} \text{grad} \cdot A - d/dt d/dt \text{partial} A$

But: $\text{grad} \times B = \epsilon_{ijk} dj eklm dl Am = dj di Aj - dj dj Ai$

Given that $A_i = v_i g \phi''$ (here v_i is only in the x direction), then A_i satisfies the same equation as ϕ , but ((12)) leads to, using the Lorentz gauge:

D'Alembertian $\phi = \text{charge density constant}$ so D'Alembertian $A = \text{current density}$ ((13))

Thus: $dE/dt \text{partial} = \text{grad} \times B + \text{constant current density}$ ((14))

Vector Nature of dE/dt

In the above, we argued that $E = -\text{grad} \phi - dA/dt \text{partial}$ exists because one wishes the vector of E to indicate isotropy in 3-space in the moving frame. Thus, $-\text{grad} \phi$ does not suffice. $dE/dt \text{partial}$ represents a change in time holding x,y,z fixed and so it too should indicate isotropy in space, i.e there should be no special weighting to x,y,z.

$$E = d\phi/dr'' (e_i (x-vt) + e_j y + e_k z)$$

$$dE/dt \text{ partial} = e_i (-v d\phi/dr'' -3 (gg(x-vt)(x-vt) (-v) d/dr'' d/dr'' \phi)$$

$$E_j y gg(x-vt)y (-v) d/dr'' d/dr'' \phi + e_k gg(x-vt)z (-v) d/dr'' d/dr'' \phi \quad ((15))$$

$$dE/dt \text{ partial} = d/dr'' d\phi/dr'' (-v)^3 (gg) (x-vt) (e_i (x-vt) + e_j y + e_k z) + d/dr'' d/dr'' \phi'' (-v) e_i$$

Thus, an r vector appears in $dE/dt \text{ partial}$ which represents isotropy, in addition to $d/dr'' \phi'' (-v) e_i$. The extra e_i term simply indicates that x of the charge center-of-mass is moving away from a fixed origin.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to argue that the four Maxwell EM equations may be obtained from the notion of spherical charge symmetry in the rest frame, special relativity and the Lorentz gauge. We argue that the Lorentz gauge is really a continuity equation for energy and momentum, i.e. represents conservation. In obtaining these results, we try to derive Gauss' law in a manner which we think is more general than that presented in (2)

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco, R., Maxwell's Laws and Lorentz Force from Special Relativity, Lorentz Gauge and Gauss' Law? (preprint, zenodo, 2024)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Gauss' Law Following from Special Relativity and the Nature of a Delta Function (preprint, zenodo, 2024)